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PROJECT REPORT

ON

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON SOCIAL & ECONOMIC STATUS OF
CONSUMER A STUDY OF CONSUMER DURABLE INDUSTRY

BY

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic and the lockdown and social distancing mandates have disrupted the consumer habits of buying as well as shopping. Consumers are learning to improvise and learn new habits. For example, consumers cannot go to the store, so the store comes to home. While consumers go back to old habits, it is likely that they will be modified by new regulations and procedures in the way consumers shop and buy products and services. New habits will also emerge by technology advances, changing demographics and innovative ways consumers have learned to cope with blurring the work, leisure, and education boundaries.

The coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic has impacted the economy, livelihood, and physical and mental well-being of people worldwide. This study aimed to compare the mental health status during the pandemic in the general population of seven middle income countries (MICs) in Asia (China, Iran, Malaysia, Pakistan, Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam).

All the countries used the Impact of Event Scale–Revised (IES-R) and Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-21) to measure mental health. There were 4479 Asians completed the questionnaire with demographic characteristics, physical symptoms and health service utilization, contact history, knowledge and concern, precautionary measure, and rated their mental health with the IES-R and DASS-21. Descriptive statistics, One-Way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and linear regression were used to identify protective and risk factors associated with mental health parameters.

There were significant differences in IES-R and DASS-21 scores between 7 MICs ($p < 0.05$). Thailand had all the highest scores of IES-R, DASS-21 stress, anxiety, and depression scores whereas Vietnam had all the lowest

scores. The risk factors for adverse mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic include age <30 years, high education background, single and separated status, discrimination by other countries and contact with people with COVID-19 ($p < 0.05$). The protective factors for mental health include male gender, staying with children or more than 6 people in the same household, employment, confidence in doctors, high perceived likelihood of survival, and spending less time on health information ($p < 0.05$). This comparative study among 7 MICs enhanced the understanding of mental health in the general population during the COVID-19 pandemic.

INTRODUCTION

CONSUMER spending has borne the brunt of COVID-19's impact on the economy. Real personal consumption expenditure (PCE), which accounts for a little less than 70% of GDP, fell by 10.1% in Q2 2020 compared to Q1 2020, the sharpest quarterly contraction on record. This contraction in demand, in turn, pushed wider economic activity down in Q2 by the most since national accounts records started.

First, worries about contracting the virus are forcing people to restrict their movements, which in turn has hit spending. And second, as the economy takes a beating, rising unemployment and worries about likely job losses in the future are prompting people to hold on to their earnings and save more.

Services bear the brunt as consumers cut spending in Q2

Consumer spending on services contracted by 13.3% in Q2, much worse than the dip in spending on durable goods (-2.9%) and nondurable goods (-4.2%). The disproportionate impact on services spending is likely due to consumers cutting back on purchases that they deem nonessential, or

because such purchases involve going to a venue where the risk of contracting the virus is relatively high. For example, spending on recreational services and on food services and accommodation has fallen sharply as consumers shy away from theaters, theme parks, restaurants, and bars (figure 1). Spending on transportation services also suffered in Q2 (-36.7%) as many people shifted to “work from home” and shunned shared forms of communal travel from taxis and other car services to airlines, buses, and subways as they tried to socially distance.

Those consumers who own luxury cars, watches and other items are considered by others as persons of higher status.

SPREAD – EFFECT

Consumer behavior has a spread effect. The buying behaviour of one person may influence the buying behavior of another person. For instance, a customer may always prefer to buy premium brands of clothing, watches and other items etc. This may influence some of his friends, neighbors, colleagues. This is one of the reasons why marketers use celebrities like Shahrukh Khan , Sachin Tendulkar to endorse their brands.

STANDARD OF LIVING

Consumer buying behaviour may lead to higher standard of living. The more a person buys the goods and services, the higher is the standard of living.

KEEPS ON CHANGING

The consumer's behaviour undergoes a change over a period of time depending upon changes in age, education and income level. Etc. for instance, kids may prefer colorful dresses, but as they grow up as teenagers and young adults, they may prefer trendy clot.

CONSUMER DURABLE INDUSTRY

The Consumer Durables industry consists of durable goods and appliances for domestic use such as televisions, refrigerators, air conditioners and washing machines. Instruments such as cellphones and kitchen appliances like microwave ovens are also included in this category. The sector has been witnessing significant growth in recent years, helped by several drivers such as the emerging retail boom, real estate and housing demand, greater disposable income and an overall increase in the level of affluence of a significant section of the population. Consumer durables refer to those consumer goods that do not quickly wear out and yields utility over a long period of time. The consumer durables industry can be broadly classified into two segments: Consumer Electronics and Consumer Appliances. Consumer Appliances can be further categorized into Brown Goods and White Goods. The key product lines under each segment are as follows.

1.White Goods

White goods mainly include air conditioners, refrigerators, washing machines, audio equipment and speakers.

2.Brown Goods

This kind of consumer durables mostly include kitchen appliances like chimneys, electric fans, grinders, iron, microwave ovens, mixers and varied other cooking ranges.

3.Consumer Electronics

Some of the mostly used consumer electronic goods are DVD players, MP3 players, mobile telephones, telephones, VCD players etc.

INDIAN CONSUMER DURABLE INDUSTRY

Evolution of consumer durables sector marked from pre-liberalization period with closed market, increased product availability, increased media penetration and advertisements. Liberalization of markets since 1991 added more importance to this sector by allowing global players such as Samsung and L.G. Since then the focus of consumer durable market shifted from promotion to product innovation. Increased availability and affordability of consumer finance also provides impetus to the growth of this sector. Indian companies such as Videocon and Philips gained global identity. Consolidation of market share by different companies led to increasing penetration of high end products like AC and Microwave ovens. Both Indian and foreign companies are very active in this field by innovating different models suitable to the preferences of urban and rural consumers. The growing importance of consumer durable goods among Indian consumers is a good indicator of high growth rate of this sector.

Emerging psychiatric conditions and mental well-being were identified as the tenth most frequent research topic during the COVID-19 pandemic. A recent systematic review found that relatively high rates of symptoms of anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder and stress were reported in the general population and health care professionals during the COVID-19 pandemic globally. Asia has a

number of middle income countries (MICs) that face tremendous economic challenges and limited medical resources to maintain physical and mental well-being during the pandemic. This extended to North America as well, with the sudden change in economic security during COVID-19 projected to increase suicide rates. During the pandemic, the Asia Pacific Disaster Mental Health Network recommended to establish a mental health agenda for Asia . It is therefore important to conduct research to assess psychiatric status of Asians living in MICs to develop capacity of various health systems to respond to COVID-19. Previous studies mainly focused on mental health of individual Asian countries during the pandemic without cross comparison.

With no prior comparative study found on physical and mental health of Asians living in MICs during the COVID-19 pandemic, this study aimed to investigate the impact of the pandemic on physical and mental health in 7 Asian MICs (China, Iran, Malaysia, Pakistan, Philippines, Thailand and Vietnam), identify differences among countries, understand their concerns and precautions toward COVID-19, as well as to identify protective and risk factors associated with mental health outcomes.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sheth et. al (2020) determined the impact of covid 19 on consumer behavior. Will the consumers permanently change their consumption habits due to lockdown and social distancing or will they go back to their old habits once the global crisis is over? The study used reliability, correlation and regression in research. The covid 19 has significantly relation between consumer behaviors. It is expected that most habits will return back to normal. However, it is inevitable that some habits will die because the consumer under the lockdown condition has discovered an alternative that is more convenient, affordable, and accessible. In conclusion the study we showed the lockdown and social distancing to combat the covid-19 virus has generated significant disruptions on consumer behavior. All consumption is time bound and location bound.

Surg et . al (2020) finds the socio-economic effect of covid 19 on individuals' aspects of world economy. the study used face validity, correlation, reliability and multiple regression. The study finds that covid 19 badly hit all the sectors badly it includes primary & secondary sector. it summarizes the effect of COVID-19 on individual aspects of the world economy, focusing on **primary sectors** which include industries involved in the extraction of raw materials, **secondary sectors**involved in the production of finished products and **tertiary sectors** including all service provision industries. In conclusion covid 19 impacts onall the sectors Immediate relief measures need to be implemented and adjusted for those that may fall through the cracks. Medium- and longer-term planning is needed to re-balance and re-energise the economy following this crisis.

Barua ,Levin et .al (2020) researched on What's weighing on consumer spending Fear of COVID-19 and its economic impact.in this research study were used analyzing tools and survey method for getting response In this analysis, multivariate models were used to determine the interaction between respondents' demographic profiles, their concerns, and their perceptions of safety with news coverage about the pandemic, and new virus cases and death rates due to COVID-19.as per the finding of this research paper the consumer has fell by 10.1% in Q2 2020 compared to Q1 2020,1 the sharpest quarterly contraction on record. This contraction in demand, in turn, pushed wider economic activity down in Q2 by the most since national accounts records started. The conclusion is that virus is still weighing on people's minds and hence, spending of consumers are also affected all over 18 countries.

Consumer spending on services contracted by 13.3% in Q2, much worse than the dip in spending on durable goods (-2.9%) and nondurable goods (-4.2%).

Prawato, Zahra et. Al (2020) studied on the Impacts of Covid-19 Pandemic on Socio-Economic Mobility in Indonesia. The purpose of this study was to examine the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on social and economic mobility occurring in Indonesia. This research conducted with the help of research paper of different scholars. the study used SPSS software program, specifically using regression and correlation. through this study researcher found that there was a strong relationship between a pandemic tested positive for COVID-19 and mortality rates with socio-economic conditions.

A consumer is a person who identifies a need or desire, makes a purchase and then disposes of the product in the consumption process. A typical consumer's utility is dependent on the consumption of agricultural and industrial goods, services, housing and wealth (Grundey, 2009). No two of them are the same, as everyone is influenced by different internal and external factors which form the consumer behaviour. Consumer behaviour is an important and constant decision-making process of searching, purchasing, using, evaluating, and disposing of products and services (Valaskova et al., 2015). The macro consumer behaviour is created by social issues, but to reach the factors of micro consumer behaviour, individual factors (Solomon, 2016) are researched. Flatters and Willmott (2009) claim consumers try to maximize their utility, satisfaction, or joy by purchasing consumer goods

Mehta, Saxena, Purohit et.al (2020) studied on the New Consumer Behaviour Paradigm amid COVID-19. This study used survey methods for collecting the data and use face validity, correlation and regression analysis. through this study researcher observed that during the pandemic, people are spending less in non-essential goods such as clothing, makeup ,shoes ,jewelry .and electronic goods. The report also stated edible products are expected to have an increased demand and non-edible products shall have a moderate need globally, thereby decreased demand which includes homecare, cosmetics and personal care products. A survey

on Indian consumer sentiments during corona virus crisis was carried out by Mckinsey from 1–4 May 2020. The result indicated that 76 per cent of consumer out of the sample strongly agreed to spend their money carefully and cut back on their purchase.

Iqbal, Ismail et.al (2011) researched on gender and socioeconomic class differences on interpersonal influence susceptibility on buying behavior. the purpose of study was gender and socio-economicstatus difference on interpersonal influence susceptibility on buying behavior of customers. the research conducted with the help of t-test andthe finding was indicate non-significant difference among females and males, but significant difference between low, middle and high socioeconomic class buyers on susceptibility to interpersonal influence and that high socioeconomic class are comparatively more susceptible.

Shashi Kiran, Madhavaiah et.al (2015) researched on impact of socio-economic status on buying behaviour of organic food products. The main objective of study was to understand the attitude of the consumer towards buying behaviour of organic food products. The study was conducted by percentage analysis, chi square test, spearman's rank correlation, Friedman test. The findings were that socio-economic status of consumers effect on their buying behaviour. The conclusion is that Consumer behaviour plays a major role in Organic food products segment.

Debnath et.al (2020) studied on impact of covid 19 on consumer purchase behaviour in retail sector. The main objective of study was that understand the impact of covid 19 on consumer in the area of awareness level of buyers, online service, huge price of products. The study used SPSS software, questionnaire, factor analysis, Cronbach's alpha. The findings provides that the independent variables highly influenced the purchase behaviour of consumer. the conclusion was that marketers, advertiser, retailers to implement future strategies according to the current pandemic situation towards consumer purchase behaviour.

Oona et.al (2020) researched on the impact of current crisis generated by the covid 19 pandemic on consumer behaviour. The paper aims to analyze the manner in which the perception and attitude of the individual towards risk causes major changes in its purchase behaviour. The study used questionnaire non probability technique, multiple regression analysis and reliability test.

The findings identified that fear and concern generated by the current economic and social crisis are visibly affecting both social behaviour in general and purchasing behavior Poudel, subed et.al (2020) researched on impact of covid 19 on socio-economic and mental health aspects in Nepal. the study used regression analysis, probability technique, interview for collecting data. The findings was that lockdown, curfews and social distancing, quarantine have affected the overall physical, mental, wellbeing and socio- economic status of consumers. the conclusion of this study was that the long-term battle may help to people to be prepare for win against numerous health diseases.

Jha, Pradhan et.al (2020) studied on factor causing change in consumer behaviour during covid 19 pandemic. The main focused of research was identifying the factor which have triggered such changes and ranking the factor based upon the factor which influenced consumer behaviour. The research used sectorial analysis, regression analysis, t-test. the findings and conclusions was that organisation should focused on building the strategies to understand the reason that change buying behaviour and must focus on boost their current sales and launch new products as per consumer purchase behaviour.

Kumar, Uma Shankar, Kim, Bhagwat et.al (2016) researched on assessing the influence of economics and consumer experience factor on service purchase behavior. The core aim of study was to understand how personal income influenced the degree to which the aggregate economic influenced the purchase behaviour. The study used reliability test, regression analysis, probability technique. The findings provides that lower income consumers are more sensitive to change in the economy than higher class income consumers and it's influenced consumer purchase behaviour.

White, C.J, Ton, E. (2019) on linking socio-economic status of consumer loyalty behaviour studied. The purpose of this study was to provide a theoretically robust explanation for the psychology process that connects occupation, income, education to loyalty. The structure interview used for data collection and structural equation modeling used for data analysis. These findings highlight the importance and potential application of a universal needs concept for expanding and deepening consumer behavior theory.

Campbell et.al (2013) researched on socio-economic status, social relationships, higher weight status . The purpose of the study was to examine the extent to which the higher weight status is patterned by indicator of socio-economic status. The research conducted with the help of national health and nutrition examination survey (2003-2008), least square regression model In finding and conclusion, results show that indicators of socioeconomic status and social relationships are associated with higher weight status.

Khan, Torpiano- , McLellan , Mahmud et.al (2020) The impact of socioeconomic-

status on 30 day mortality in hospitalized patients with COVID 19 infection research conducted with the purpose- of compare the outcome of hospitalized coronavirus disease 219 (COVID 19) patients in low and high SES group. The research used Scottish index for multiple deprivation (SIMD) , spearman's rank correlation. SES- does not have any impact on outcome of hospitalized patients with COVID 19, however it negatively impacts length of stay.

Gopalan, Mishra et.al (2020) conducted research on COVID-19 pandemic and challenges for socio-economic issues, healthcare and National Health Programs in India with the aim of discuss socio-economic, health and National healthcare challenges following lockdown, with focus on population belonging to low socio-economic stratum (SES) . The research used with pub web and Google scholar, regression analysis. The findings provide nationwide lockdown has resulted in financial losses and has affected all segments of society. The conclusion was that Apart from firm economic measures, all National Health Programs should be re-strengthened

Chand , Chandra , Hindu , Singhal et.al (2020) researched on Impact of COVID-19 on Socio-Economic State of Indian Farmers. The objective of study was analyze the various approaches which affected social and economic state of Indian farmers. The study used probability technique, questionnaire, multiple regression model. The findings provided that Indian government has more challenges ahead because about 85% of total Indian farm households are being small and marginal, and significantly high proportion of landless farmworkers.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of covid 19 on socioeconomic status of consumers: A Study of consumer durable industry. The questionnaires were filled by the peoples in Gwalior and by applying test like reliability and regression the data was Analyzed. It has been concluded that there is huge impact of covid 19 on socioeconomic status of consumers so it also impacting the business of consumer durable industry. Immediate relief measures need to be implemented and adjusted for those that may fall through the cracks. Medium- and longer-term planning is needed to re-balance and re-energize the economy following this crisis. A broad socioeconomic development plan including sector by sector plans and an ecosystem that encourages entrepreneurship is also needed so that those with robust and sustainable business models can flourish. This study reflects the high degree of impact of covid 19 (dependent variable) on socioeconomic status (independent variable) of consumers. With fears of a new recession and financial collapse, times like these call for resilient and strong leadership in healthcare, business, government and wider society. Immediate relief measures need to be implemented and adjusted for those that may fall through the cracks. Medium and longer term planning is needed to re-balance and re-energise the economy following this crisis. A broad socioeconomic development plan including sector by sector plans and an ecosystem that encourages entrepreneurship is also needed so that those with robust and sustainable business models can flourish. It is prudent that governments and financial institutions constantly re-assess and re-evaluate the state of play and ensure that the '*whatever it takes*' promise is truly delivered.

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